

WP4.4.8 – Recommendations and Application Profile Proposal for archaeological remote and near-surface sensing data in ARIADNEplus

Version 1.0 (final)

15.3.2022

Grant Agreement number: 823914

Project acronym: ARIADNEplus

Project title: Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe - plus

Funding Scheme: H2020-INFRAIA-2018-1

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The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Community's Horizon 2020 Programme (H2020-INFRAIA-2018-1) under grant agreement n° 823914.

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These recommendations were prepared through the [ipaast-czo](#) project, which aims to improve the interoperability of remote and near-surface sensing data between archaeological and precision agricultural applications. The ipaast-czo project is funded by the [British Academy](#), award KF5210407.

Document History

- 15.03.2022 – Final Version 1.0

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1 Executive Summary

The objective of this report is to make recommendations that will increase the **findability** of these data by users from domains outside archaeology by using **AAT vocabulary terms shared with non-archaeological domains** and improving the **reusability** of the data through **prioritising metadata** most relevant to data analysis and interpretation.

2 Introduction and Objectives

Archaeological remote and near-surface sensing data (ARNSS) data is produced through the application of a range of techniques e.g., colour photography, LiDAR, multispectral imaging, ground-penetrating radar, and magnetic gradiometry, using satellite, aerial, and terrestrial platforms, to assess the potential preservation of, detect the presence of and characterising the properties of subsurface or surface archaeological remains. These data have significant potential for reuse in the context of integrated land management, sustainable land management, and the promotion of landscape heritage. Their reuse potential beyond archaeology is high because they include information on the geophysical, geochemical and geotechnical character of buried soils, the inclusion of anthropogenic materials in buried soils, modifications of the morphology of the land's surface, and the impacts of modifications to soils and surface morphology on plant communities.

The objective of this report is to make recommendations that will increase the **findability** of these data by users from domains outside archaeology by using **AAT vocabulary terms shared with non-archaeological domains** and improving the **reusability** of the data through **prioritising metadata** most relevant to data analysis and interpretation.

Remote sensing data is a special case within scientific and geospatial data and this report, therefore, builds on the work and recommendations of the ARIADNEplus subtask 4.4.10, which address geospatial and GIS data. The final report by WP4.4.10 on geospatial data in archaeology noted two ways in which discoverability should be increased, broadly by making ARNSS data findable outside archaeology and by making a wider range of data relevant to ARNSS findable by archaeologists. Their report frames this as discoverability of geospatial:

1. **Archaeological data** which are available in a standardized form and easy to integrate with other spatial data for any use-case even outside archaeology.
2. **Proxy-data** (e.g. elevation data, historical climate data, hydrology data, old maps etc.) useful for archaeologists in specific fields and regions, which can contextualise their own research data and are made available by non-archaeological service providers.

This report addresses #1 – Making geospatial archaeological data more findable and reusable outside archaeology for the specific case of ARNSS data. Improving the findability and reusability of non-archaeological remote and near-surface sensing data for archaeologists will be addressed in a separate report.

This report makes specific recommendations for future data providers mapping their data to ARIADNE plus. The recommendations address:

- Distinguishing Data and Reports.

- Key metadata elements beyond those included in AO_Cat entries.

Selecting AAT subject mappings to maximise findability outside archaeology and heritage management.

3 AO_Cat and ARNSS data

Any ARNSS dataset is considered to be an AO_Cat: AO_Data_Resource. When supplying ARNSS datasets, core metadata elements such as author, location, dataset description, and publisher should be supplied following the relevant AO_Cat schema. The recommendations here are for additional metadata elements to be supplied in addition to project level information which would normally be included through AO_Cat entries.

4 Distinguishing between Raw Data, Processed Data, and Reports in ARNSS AO_Data_Resources

ARNSS data falls into two resource types used within the ARIADNE system: raw and processed data fall under the type 'Fieldwork archive' and vectorised interpretations and descriptions fall under the type 'fieldwork report'. Consequently, the AO_Data_Resource > has_type > either Fieldwork Archive or Fieldwork Report. Because the ways in which they can be reused are significantly different, it is important to distinguish between the two resource types and to assign data to the correct category.

Fieldwork Archive: Datasets that contain what is commonly referred to as 'raw', calibrated/cleaned, or processed data constitute fieldwork archives. In these datasets, measured values or values produced through a calculation or analysis of the measured values are represented. These data can be geolocated. Examples of fieldwork archive items include orthorectified vertical aerial photographs, georeferenced oblique aerial photographs, georeferenced GPR time slices, and georeferenced sky view factor visualisations of lidar-derived terrain models.

Fieldwork Report: Datasets that contain the products of archaeological interpretations of ARNSS data constitute fieldwork reports. Examples of fieldwork report items include written reports containing illustrations and commentary, non-geolocated images, and georeferenced or non-georeferenced vector data (e.g. points, polylines, polygons with associated attributes) representing the archaeological interpretations of anomalies in ARNSS data.

Both fieldwork archives and fieldwork reports have good potential for reuse in archaeological and cultural heritage management applications. To improve the **reusability** of ARNSS data in applications outside of archaeology and cultural heritage management, this report recommends that contributors submit metadata for **fieldwork archive** datasets to ARIADNEplus whenever feasible.

5 ARNSS metadata elements required in addition to the AO_CAT core elements

For **raw, calibrated, and processed data**, the Archaeological Data Service provides full guidance for ideal metadata which covers the most common types of ARNSS data under the headings of:

- [Aerial Survey](#)
- [UAV Survey](#)
- [Geophysics](#)
- [Laser Scanning](#)

The metadata recommended under these standards is extensive. In practice, the availability in contributors' archives of full metadata which meets these standards is inconsistent. To improve the reusability of fieldwork archive datasets while minimising the workload implied in retrofitting metadata, this report recommends a set of minimal metadata elements. The selected elements are focused on the information needed to perform analysis and interpretation. All recommended elements are mapped to the CRM, Heritage Science, or CRMSci application ontologies and no new terms are needed. These elements should be provided in addition to the AO_CAT:AO_Data_Resource elements and any other relevant AO_CAT elements.

Key AO_CAT elements are:

- Dataset (AO_CAT:AO_Data_Resource)
- Survey Project (AO_Cat: AO_Event)
- Practitioners (AO_Cat:AO_Agent)
- Survey Location (AO_Cat:AO_Spatial_Region)
- Survey Period (AO_Cat:AO_Temporal_Region)

The recommended additional metadata elements for all **'raw' Fieldwork Archives** of ARNSS data include:

- Survey type (CRMHS:Analysis)
- Instrumentation (CRMHS:Device)
- Instrument Setting - X-axis resolution (aka Scale, Nominal Line separation or cross-line spacing) in meters or unitless if scale (CRMHS:Protocol)
- Instrument Setting - Y-axis resolution (aka Scale, Nominal Reading interval or in-line spacing) in meters or unitless if scale (CRMHS:Protocol)

- Instrument Setting - Z-axis resolution (aka Scale, vertical measurement interval, above or below surface) in meters or unitless if scale i(CRMHS:Protocol)
- Instrument Setting - Coordinate system (CRMGEO:SP4 Spatial Coordinate Reference System)
- Indication of raw (instrument values), calibrated / cleaned, post-processed; interpretation status (CRMHS:Analysis > has_type)
- File format (a non-proprietary file format is required) (CRMHS:Dataset > has_format)

The following method-specific metadata elements are recommended for **'raw' Fieldwork Archives** of ARNSS data:

For GPR:

- Antenna type (instrument settings - CRMHS:Device_Component)
- Timing information (instrument settings - CRMHS:Protocol)
- Average subsurface velocity (instrument settings - CRMHS:Protocol)

For EMI / EC:

- Coil configuration (instrument settings - CRMHS:Device_Component)
- Recorded component (instrument settings - CRMHS:Protocol)

For Magnetic gradiometry and susceptibility:

- Magnetic north (instrument settings - CRMHS:Protocol)
- Instrument drift value (instrument settings - CRMHS:Protocol)

For spectroscopy, spectral imaging and thermal imaging data:

- Spectral resolution (instrument settings - CRMHS:Protocol)
- spectral range (instrument settings - CRMHS:Protocol)
- Calibration system (instrument settings - CRMHS:Protocol)
- Reference datasets (instrument settings - CRMHS:Protocol)

The following method-specific metadata elements are recommended for **'processed' Fieldwork Archives** of ARNSS data:

For lidar data derivatives:

- Classification method (Processing method - CRMHS:Protocol)
- Visualisation method (Processing method - CRMHS:Protocol)

For any other data processed beyond raw instrument values:

- Plain language statement on the processing protocol (Processing method - CRMHS:Protocol)

The recommended additional metadata elements for all **Fieldwork Reports** on ARNSS data, including **georeferenced interpreted vectors representing anomalies**, are:

- Survey type (Interpretation - CRMHS:Analysis)
- Reference to the fieldwork archive, if available. (CRMHS:analysed > CRMHS:Dataset)
- Plain language statement on vectorisation methodology, interpretive categories used, or a reference to the standard vocabulary used (Interpretation - CRMHS:Protocol)

6 Application Profile

The proposed application profile extends the AO_Cat and uses elements of the CRM, CRMSci and proposed Heritage Science (HS) application ontologies. No new entities are required, but updates to scope notes for clarity may be merited. The core components are visualised in diagram form for workflows without calibration.

The proposed application profile extends the AO_Cat and uses elements of the CRM, CRMSci and proposed Heritage Science (HS) application ontologies. No new entities are required, but updates to scope notes for clarity may be merited. The core components are visualised in diagram form through the fieldwork report stage for workflows with calibration.

8 Recommended AAT vocabulary tags

In order to maximise **findability** beyond archaeology for targeted applications in integrated land management and sustainable land management, the following AAT subjects are recommended as tags. Because each contributors' archive will have different native subject tags or lack native tags, these recommendations are made based on the survey type (method/properties measured). This information is readily identifiable in current ARIADNE datasets returned by a search with keywords 'geophysical survey' or 'aerial survey'.

Method	Recommended AAT subjects	Further relevant AAT subjects
Magnetic gradiometry	Archaeology; landscape archaeology; geoarchaeology; Landscapes (environments); Soil; Geomagnetism; magnetic surveying	Cultural landscapes; Historic landscapes; Environmentally sensitive area; Soil, borrow;
Electromagnetic Induction (EMI)	Archaeology; landscape archaeology; geoarchaeology; Landscapes (environments); Soil; Soil permeability; Moisture content; Salinity; magnetic surveying	Cultural landscapes; Historic landscapes; Environmentally sensitive area; Soil, borrow; Drainage;
Electric Conductivity (EC)	Archaeology; landscape archaeology; geoarchaeology; Landscapes (environments); Soil; Soil permeability; Moisture content; Salinity; Conductivity; resistivity surveying	Cultural landscapes; Historic landscapes; Environmentally sensitive area; Soil, borrow; Drainage;

Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR)	<p>Archaeology; landscape archaeology; geoarchaeology;</p> <p>Landscapes (environments);</p> <p>Soil; Density</p>	<p>Cultural landscapes;</p> <p>Historic landscapes;</p> <p>Environmentally sensitive area;</p> <p>Soil, borrow; Drainage; Compaction;</p>
Method	Recommended AAT subjects	Further relevant AAT subjects
Magnetic Susceptibility	<p>Archaeology; landscape archaeology; geoarchaeology;</p> <p>Landscapes (environments);</p> <p>Soil; Geomagnetism; magnetic surveying</p>	<p>Cultural landscapes;</p> <p>Historic landscapes;</p> <p>Environmentally sensitive area;</p> <p>Soil, borrow</p>
Aerial Photography	<p>Archaeology; landscape archaeology;</p> <p>Landscapes (environments); aerial surveying</p>	<p>geoarchaeology;</p> <p>Cultural landscapes;</p> <p>Historic landscapes;</p> <p>Environmentally sensitive area; Crop marks; vegetation; Drainage; Moisture content;</p>

<p>Lidar</p>	<p>Archaeology; landscape archaeology;</p> <p>Landscapes (environments);</p> <p>Soil mechanics; airborne laser scanning; aerial surveying</p>	<p>geoarchaeology; Cultural landscapes;</p> <p>Historic landscapes;</p> <p>Environmentally sensitive area;</p> <p>Drainage;</p>
<p>Multi or hyperspectral imagery</p>	<p>Archaeology; landscape archaeology;</p> <p>Landscapes (environments); aerial surveying; Soil; Geoarchaeology; Moisture content</p>	<p>geoarchaeology; Cultural landscapes;</p> <p>Historic landscapes;</p> <p>Environmentally sensitive area;</p> <p>Soil; Crop marks; vegetation</p>
<p>Thermal imagery</p>	<p>Archaeology; landscape archaeology;</p> <p>Landscapes (environments); Thermal stability; aerial surveying</p>	<p>geoarchaeology; Cultural landscapes;</p> <p>Historic landscapes;</p> <p>Environmentally sensitive area;</p> <p>Soil; Crop marks; Drainage;</p>